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GROWTH OF UNORGANIZED SECTOR IN INDIA A STUDY ON MICRO FINANCE AND POVERTY REDUCTION IN INDIA

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Abstract

India falls under low income class according to World Bank. It is second populated country in the world and around 70 % of its population lives in rural area. 60% of people depend on agriculture, as a result there is chronic underemployment and per capita income is only \$ 3262. This is not enough to provide food to more than one individual. The obvious result is abject poverty, low rate of education, low sex ratio, and exploitation. The major factor account for high incidence of rural poverty is the low asset base. According to Reserve Bank of India, about 51 % of people house possess only 10% of the total asset of India .This has resulted low production capacity both in agriculture (which contribute around 22-25% of GDP) and Manufacturing sector. Rural people have very low access to institutionalized credit (from commercial bank).

Key terms: - Micro Finance, Financial Services, Poverty, NGOs, India.

Introduction

Microfinance is the provision of financial services to low-income clients, including consumers and the self-employed, who traditionally lack access to banking and related services. More broadly, it is a movement whose object is “a world in which as many poor and near-poor households as possible have permanent access to an appropriate range of high quality financial services, including not just credit but also savings, insurance, and fund transfers.” Those who promote microfinance generally believe that such access will help poor people out of poverty.

Micro credit emphasizes the provision of credit services to low income clients, usually in the form of small loans for micro enterprise and income generating activities. Use of the term ‘micro credit’ is often associated with an inadequate amount of the value of savings for the poor. In most cases, the provision of savings services in ‘micro credit’ schemes simply involves the collection of compulsory deposit amounts that are designed only to collateralize those loans. Additional voluntary savings may collect but the clients have restricted access to their enforced savings. These savings become the main source of capital in the financial institutions.

Microfinance is considered as a tool for socio-economic development and can be clearly distinguished from charity. Families who are destitute or so poor they are unlikely to be able to generate the cash flow required to repay a loan, should be recipients of charity. Others are best served by financial institutions.

A Profile of Rural India

- 350 million Below Poverty Line
- 95 % have no access to microfinance.
- 56 % people still borrow from informal sources.
- 70 % don't have any deposit account.
- 87 % no access to credit from formal sources.
- Annual credit demand is about Rs.70,000 crores.
- 95 % of the households are without any kind of insurance.
- Informally Microfinance has been in practice for ages.

Role of Microfinance in Poverty Reduction:

Microfinance is about providing financial services to the poor who are not served by the Conventional formal financial institutions - it is about extending the frontiers of financial service provision. The provision of such financial services requires innovative delivery channels and methodologies. The needs for financial services that allow people to both take advantage of opportunities and better management of their resources. Microfinance can be one effective tool amongst many for poverty alleviation. However, it should be used with caution -despite recent claims, the equation between microfinance and poverty alleviation is not straight-forward, because poverty is a complex phenomenon and many constraints that the poor in general have to cope with. We need to understand when and in what form microfinance is appropriate for the poorest; the delivery channel, methodology and products offered are all inter-linked and in turn affect the prospect and promise of poverty alleviation. Access to formal banking services is difficult for the poor. The main problem the poor have to take when trying to acquire loans from formal financial institutions is the demand for collateral asked by these institutions. In addition, the process of acquiring a loan entails many bureaucratic procedures, which lead to extra transaction costs for the poor. Formal financial institutions are not motivated to lend money to them. In general, formal financial institutions show a preference for urban over rural sectors, large-scale over small scale transactions, and non-agricultural over agricultural loans.

Rural India and Microfinance

Micro financing has become important since the possibility of a sub-Rs 1,000 mobile handset has been ruled out in the near future. Rural India can generally afford handsets in the price range of Rs 1,500-2,000. To succeed in India, agribusiness must empower the farmer by making agriculture profitable, not by expropriating him for this particular purpose the farmer should be funded for their basic and small needs.

Micro finance is expected to play a significant role in poverty alleviation and development. The need, therefore, is to share experiences and materials which will help not only in understanding successes and failures but also provide knowledge and guidelines to strengthen and expand micro finance programmes. The development process through a typical micro-finance intervention can be understood with the help of the following Chart. The ultimate aim is to attain social and economic empowerment. Successful intervention is therefore, dependent on how each of these stages has been carefully dealt with and also the capabilities of the implementing organizations in achieving the final goal, e.g., if credit delivery takes place without consolidation of SHGs, it may have problems of self-sustainability and recovery. A number of schemes under banks, central and state governments offer direct credit to potential individuals without forcing them to join SHGs. Compilation and classification of the communication materials in the directory is done based on this development process.

Sustainable Micro Finance-features and Principles:

Microfinance is considered to be an adequate tool for financing small scale activities/technological applications in the rural areas because of the following features.

- (a) Provide credit for investment in small scale activities chosen by the poor people.
- (b) Empower the poor to build self confidence that I can do something.
- (c) Can pay for itself with the interest earned.
- (d) Allow to develop opportunities for self employment to the underserved people.
- (e) Have the broadest utility and the least cost per beneficiary.

The principles of sustainable micro-financing are as follows:

- (i) It offers flexible customer friendly services preferred by low-income group,
- (ii) It has opportunities for streamlining operations and reducing costs (standardized simple lending process, decentralized loan approval, inexpensive offices, and use staff from local communities)

- (iii) It operates in market basis charging market interest rates and fees, and
- (iv) It strives to recover the costs of the loan.

Few Schemes of a Government of India:

There are so many schemes for the up-liftment of poor In India. One of them Micro-credit programmes is run primarily by NABARD in the field of agriculture and SIDBI in the field of Industry, Service and Business (ISB).

The success of Micro-credit programme lies in diversification of services. Micro Finance Scheme of SIDBI is under operation since January, 1999 with a corpus of Rs. 100 crore and a network of about 190 capacity assessed rated MFIs/NGOs. Under the programme, total amount of Rs. 191 crore have been sanctioned up to 31st December, 2003, benefiting over 9 lakh beneficiaries.

Under the programme, NGOs/ MFIs are supposed to provide equity support in order to avail SIDBI finance. But they find it difficult to manage the needed equity support because of their poor financial condition. The problem has got aggravated due to declining interest rate on deposits. The office of the development commissioner (Small Scale Industries)

Under Ministry of SSI is launching a new scheme of Micro Finance Programme to overcome the constraints in the existing scheme of SIDBI, whose reach is currently very low. It is felt that Government's role can be critical in expanding reach of the scheme, ensuring long term sustainability of NGOs /MFIs and development of Intermediaries for identification of viable projects.

Salient Features of Micro-finance Programme of Government of India:

- a) Arranging Fixed Deposits for MFIs/NGOs: Under this scheme government of India arrange money to MFI/NGO like SIDBI for micro credit to poor.
- b) Training and Studies on Micro-Finance Programme: Government of India would help SIDBI in meeting the training needs of NGOs, SHGs, intermediaries and entrepreneurs and also in enhancing awareness about the programme. Institution building for 'intermediaries' for identification of viable projects: The Government of India would help in institution building through identification and development of 'intermediary organization', which would help the NGOs/SHGs in identification of product, preparation of project report, working out forward and back ward linkages and in fixing marketing/ technology tie-ups. The SISIs would help in the identification of such intermediaries in different areas.
- c) Budgetary Provision for the Scheme During 10th plan: There was a budgetary provision in 10th five year plan and hoping more funds in next plan.
- d) Administrative arrangement: A committee has been formed to control and monitor the administrative arrangement of MFI/NGOs.

Success Factors of Micro-Finance in Rural India

Over the last ten years, successful experiences in providing finance to small entrepreneur and producers demonstrate that poor people, when given access to responsive and timely financial services at market rates, repay their loans and use the proceeds to increase their income and assets. This is not surprising since the only realistic alternative for them is to borrow from informal market at an interest much higher than market rates. Community banks, NGOs and grass root savings and credit groups around the world have shown that these micro enterprise loans can be profitable for borrowers and for the lenders, making microfinance one of the most effective poverty reducing strategies.

For NGOs

- The field of development itself expands and shifts emphasis with the pull of ideas, and NGOs perhaps more readily adopt new ideas, especially if the resources required are small, entry and exit are easy, tasks are (perceived to be) simple and people's acceptance is high – all characteristics (real or presumed) of microfinance.
- Canvassing by various actors, including the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI), Friends of Women's

World Banking (FWWB), Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK), Council for Advancement of People's Action and Rural Technologies (CAPART), Rashtriya Gramin Vikas Nidhi (RGVN), various donor funded programmes especially by the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), World Bank and Department for International Development, UK (DFID)], and lately commercial banks, has greatly added to the idea pull. Induced by the worldwide focus on microfinance, donor NGOs too have been funding microfinance projects. One might call it the supply push.

- All kinds of things from khadi spinning to Nadep compost to balwadis do not produce such concrete results and sustained interest among beneficiaries as microfinance. Most NGO-led microfinance is with poor women, for whom access to small loans to meet dire emergencies is a valued outcome. Thus, quick and high 'customer satisfaction' is the USP that has attracted NGOs to this trade.

B. For Financial Institutions and banks

Microfinance has been attractive to the lending agencies because of demonstrated sustainability and of low costs of operation. Institutions like SIDBI and NABARD are hard nosed bankers and would not work with the idea if they did not see a long term engagement – which only comes out of sustainability (that is economic attractiveness). On the supply side, it is also true that it has all the trappings of a business enterprise, its output is tangible and it is easily understood by the mainstream. This also seems to sound nice to the government, which in the post liberalisation era is trying to explain the logic of every rupee spent. That is the reason why microfinance has attracted mainstream institutions like no other developmental project. Perhaps the most important factor that got banks involved is what one might call the policy push. Given that most of our banks are in the public sector, public policy does have some influence on what they will or will not do. In this case, policy was followed by diligent, if meandering, promotional work by NABARD. The policy change about a decade ago by RBI to allow banks to lend to SHGs was initially followed by a seven-page memo by NABARD to all bank chairmen, and later by sensitisation and training programmes for bank staff across the country. Several hundred such programmes were conducted by NGOs alone, each involving 15 to 20 bank staff, all paid for by NABARD. The policy push was sweetened by the NABARD refinance scheme that offers much more favourable terms (100% refinance, wider spread) than for other rural lending by banks. NABARD also did some system setting work and banks lately have been given targets. The canvassing, training, refinance and close follow up by NABARD has resulted in widespread bank involvement.

Marketing of Microfinance Products

Contract Farming and Credit Bundling

- Banks and financial institutions have been partners in contract farming schemes, set up to enhance credit. Basically, this is a doable model. Under such an arrangement, crop loans can be extended under tie-up arrangements with corporate for production of high quality produce with stable marketing arrangements provided – and only, provided – the price setting mechanism for the farmer is appropriate and fair.

Agri Service Centre – Rabo India

- Rabo India Finance Pvt Ltd. has established agri-service centres in rural areas in cooperation with a number of agri-input and farm services companies. The services provided are similar to those in contract farming, but with additional flexibility and a wider range of products including inventory finance. Besides providing storage facilities, each centre rents out farm machinery, provides agricultural inputs and information to farmers, arranges credit, sells other services and provides a forum for farmers to market their products.

Non Traditional Markets

- Similarly, Mother Dairy Foods processing, a wholly owned subsidiary of National Dairy Development Board (NDDB) has established auction markets for horticulture producers in Bangalore. The operations and maintenance of the market is done by NDDB. The project, with an outlay of Rs.15 lakh, covers 200

horticultural farmers associations with 50,000 grower members for wholesale marketing. Their produce is planned with production and supply assurance and provides both growers and buyers a common platform to negotiate better rates.

Apni Mandi

• Another innovation is that of The Punjab Mandi Board, which has experimented with a 'farmers' market' to provide small farmers located in proximity to urban areas, direct access to consumers by elimination of middlemen. This experiment known as "Apni Mandi" belongs to both farmers and consumers, who mutually help each other. Under this arrangement a sum of Rs. 5.2 lakh is spent for providing plastic crates to 1000 farmers. Each farmer gets 5 crates at a subsidized rate. At the mandi site, the Board provides basic infrastructure facilities. At the farm level, extension services of different agencies are pooled in. These include inputs subsidies, better quality seeds and loans from Banks. Apni Mandi scheme provides self-employment to producers and has eliminated social inhibitions among them regarding the retail sale of their produce.

Conclusion:

Micro credit and microfinance have received extensive recognition as a strategy for poverty reduction and for economic empowerment. Microfinance is a way for fighting poverty, particularly in rural areas, where most of the world's poorest people live. Accessing small amounts of credit at reasonable interest rates give poor people an opportunity to set up their own small business. Many studies show that poor people are trustworthy, with higher repayment rates than conventional borrowers. When poor people have access to financial services, they can earn more, build their assets, and cushion themselves against external shocks. Poor households use microfinance to move from everyday survival to planning for the future: they invest in better nutrition, housing, health, and education. Most poor people cannot get good financial services that meet their needs because there are not enough strong institutions that provide such services. Strong institutions need to charge enough to cover their costs. Cost recovery is not an end in itself. Rather, it is the only way to reach scale and impact beyond the limited levels that donors can fund. A financially sustainable institution can continue and expand its services over the long term. Achieving sustainability means lowering transaction costs, offering services that are more useful to the clients, and finding new ways to provide banking services to the poor. At the end it should be mentioned that Poor people with no income or means of repayment need other kinds of support before they can make good use of loans. In many cases, other tools will alleviate poverty better—for instance, small grants, employment and training programs, or infrastructure improvements. Where possible, such services should be coupled with building savings. It shows that access and efficient provision of micro credit can enable the poor to smooth their consumption, better manage their risks better, gradually build their assets, develop their micro enterprises, enhance their income earning capacity and enjoy an improved quality of life. Microfinance services can also contribute to the improvement of resource allocation, promotion of markets, and adoption of better technology; thus, micro finance helps to promote economic growth and development.

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